

Covid-19 Questionnaire

You have been selected to participate in this research as a stakeholder in choosing measures to prevent the spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. The present study aims to develop and apply a multi-criteria and participatory model for the decision-making process, in conditions of increased uncertainty, regarding the management of the current pandemic. Our goal is to support decision-makers' response to future "waves" of the COVID-19 pandemic as well as of other possible pandemics in the future.

This is a part of the European Union-funded project from European Open Science Cloud EOSC, Covid-19 Fast Track Funding led by Innovating Governance, a non-profit organisation in Vienna, Austria, whose team consists of international researchers affiliated with numerous prestigious academic institutions. Find out more about us here: <https://www.igovernance.eu/about>.

Participation in this study is voluntary, and the duration of completing the questionnaire is 1-5 minutes. The answers provided will be anonymous unless you wish to be recognized as an expert in our subsequent publications, in which case please confirm your option by e-mail to adriana.mihai@iis.unibuc.ro. Innovating Governance will retain the data provided only for their processing and interpretation, without distributing them to third parties. The results of this questionnaire will be presented publicly only in the form of useful analyses and interpretations for the decision-making model.

Continuing and completing this questionnaire is your consent for the collection, storage, and processing of the information you provide by Innovating Governance.

For any questions about this research or technical issues of the questionnaire, please contact us at the address mentioned. Thank you for your participation and interest.

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* Required

5. Impacts on economy *

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

6. Impacts on education *

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

7. Well-being *

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

8. Your suggested criterion *

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Thank you for your contribution!

9. If you want to receive the report after finalisation, please write your email below. The email will not be linked to your answers in the report.

10. Thank you for responding this questionnaire. If you want to add anything or have further questions or comments, you can use the text box below or email: adriana.mihai@lils.unibuc.ro.

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